

Balehonnur is a Historical and Spiritual Destination - A Study

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Balehonnur is a most important spiritual as well as religious place in Karnataka and also it is one of the best education centre in the state. It is located in Chikkamagaluru dist 250 kilometre away from capital city of Karnataka. It is the land of coffee garden, situated in the malnad region of Karnataka. It is endowed with the rich and veritable geographical and climatically diversity, which can be truly termed as matchless and scenic beauty. Balehonnur is witnessed with ancient religious mutt i.e. Sri Rambapuri Mutt.

Sri Rambapuri Mutt is one of the most important ancient mutt of Karnataka. It was founded by His Holiness Shree 1008 Jagadguru Prasanna Veerasomeshwara Shivacharya Swamiji. His intention was to propagate human values, maintenance of peace, harmony and spiritual ideas in the society. Now it has been headed by Shree Jagduru Prasanna Renuka veera Someswara Shivacharya Swamiji. He has made shri Kshethra Balehonnur the most attractive spiritual centre and uphold the spiritual ideas. Apart from all these spiritual aspect, the Mutt is running schools and colleges for the needy class of the society. It is also carrying out a number of social activities. In this paper an attempt is made to discuss about the history of the mutt., its founder and purpose, also examine the glorious contributions and message to the society.

“Any Society, which desires to be healthy in all aspects must be having clear concept of God backed by exemplary conduct religion culture, proper insight in moral and philosophical concept, coupled with an excellence mix of scientific knowledge with excellent reasoning” by- Shree 1008 Jagduru Sri Veera Someshwara Rajadeshikendra Shivacharya Bhagavatpada

Sri Rambapuri mutt at Balehonnur is one of the famous Veerashaiva religious centre of Karnataka. Shree 1008 Jagduru Prasanna Veerasomeshwara Shivacharya Swamiji was the first Mutthadyaksha of the mutt. He preached 101 Shatssthalas of “Siddantha sikamani” the religious book of Veerashaivism. The mutt is located at Balehonnur, in Chikkamagaluru Dist. It is the land of coffee garden, situated in the malnad region of Karnataka. It is endowed with the rich and veritable geographical and climatically diversity, which can be truly termed as matchless and scenic beauty.

The Veerashivism had its own unique philosophy, literature and culture as the basic aspect for the peaceful and prosperous life. In order to propagate these philosophic aspect, the mutt was established at Balehonnur by His Holiness Shree 1008 Jdguru Prasanna Veerasomeshwara Shivacharya Swamiji. whose endeavour to bring into reality in fast changing human values and society as whole and to propagate the spiritual values. The mutt is the first and foremost institution among the five veerashaiva mutts, other Muttas are Sri Ujjain mutt, sri Kedarnath mutt, Srishaila mutt and sri Kashi mutt. It assumes rare distinction for its magnanimous multifaced religious, cultural and social development activities. Thistraditions of Veerashaiva sect was founded by five Ascetics Revana, Marula, Ekorama, Panditaradya and viswaradya. These are regarded as very ancient faith in 12th century. The gothrakaras established five great religious centers in different parts of India. Renukacharya at Balehonnur, Ekorama at Kedar, Revanna at Kashi, Panditharadya at Shrishaila, Marula at Ujjain.

121 seers have reigned at the Balehonnur mutt. Shree Jagadguru Prasanna Renuka veera Someswara Shivacarya Swamiji is the present muttheadhyaksha of the mutt. The average tenure 30 years of each jagadguru we can be witness a history of over 3600 years after established of the mutt and its rich legacy. It has become the most attractive pilgrim centre due to the three prominent deities namely, Sri Kshethranath and Gothrapurusha, Shri Veerabhadra Tempe, Shakthi mutta, sri choudeshwari Temple, Shri Jagadguru Renukacharya as one of the glorious forms of God in the Temple. These three temples have made this place an important pilgrim and spiritual centre.

Sri Jagadguru Renukacharya established Sri Rambapuri mutt at Balehonnur, and gave a proper legislative shape and appointed shivacharya for the spread of the activities of veerashaivism. To carry out the important social and religious activities. The ruling dynasties of Karnataka like Vijayanagar, Keladi Nayakas, Rastrakutas, Wodeyars of Mysore etc,. Had given grants and endowments to conduct religious activities

Shri Jagadguru Prasanna Renuka veera Someswara Shivacharya Swamiji, the 121th muttadyaksha of the mutt assumed charge on 6thfeb 1992. On the occasion of becoming the head of the mutt he made eight declarations in the presence of the devotees. The 'Astasankalpa' (8 Faiths) are as follows.

1. Dasoha (free feeding), to provide free feeding facility for devotees and students
2. To ensure good administration.
3. To establish Gurukula.
4. To encourage educational and cultural activities across the state.
5. In order to strengthen literary activity, patronage to be given to the writers.
6. By using available media the mutt has to establish its own image to the conman people.
7. To ensure a good relationship between the mutt and people, it is proposed to hold a discussion on every Shravana month of the year.
8. Arranging holy darshan to the devotees on every full moon day. All these eight Astasankalpa have been following systematically in the mutt till today.

The Activities of the Mutt

The mutt which has become an important religious centre in the state is also providing encouragement to education and social activities like other mutts in the state. From the day of his holiness coronation, he has been rendering valuable service. This task has made to attain the highest place among other mutts. His holiness inspired the millions of devotees from all section of the society, to embrace and adopt the spiritual ideas of the mutt. Because of all these spiritual aspect of the mutt headed by Shri Jagadguru Prasanna Renuka veera Someswara Shivacarya Swamiji. The reputation of the mutt has secured its highest status and created an ideal spiritual environment.

In order to ensure social and educational facilities to the people the mutt has established various organizations in the state. To strengthen these organizations economically the mutt has established commercial complex, Kalyanamantapas and Credit co-operate Societies in different parts of Karnataka like Balehonnur, Narasimharajapura, Hassan, Hubli etc. to uphold the social activities the mutt runs several important social institutions as follows

1. Sri Rambapuri Jagduru Shivananda Ashrama Trust Birur.
2. Sri Jagadguru Renukacharya Charitable trust Balehonnur.
3. Sri Jagadguru Renukacharya nithya Dasoha trust Rambapuri.
4. Sri Jagadguru Abhinava Renuka mandira Davanagere.
5. Sri Jagadguru Renukacharya kalyana mantapa Chickmagaluru
6. Sri Rambapuri Jagduru Veera gangadhara gadduge trust
7. Sri Jagadguru Renukamandira Haveri.
8. Sri Jagadguru Renukacharya mangala mandira. Kustagi and Hubli
9. Malenad Development Community Bhavan
10. Sri Kolanapaka Someswara Jagadguru Renukacharya Development Charitable Trust, Kollipaka Andhrapradesh

Shri Jagadguru Prasanna Renuka veera Someswara Shivacarya Swamiji on becoming the mutthadyaksha of the mutt his holiness has been rendering selfless service for the overall development of the society, under his guidance the mutt had actively involved in the rehabilitations work of earth quake hit area of Gujarath in 2000, and the mutt had contributed to the relief fund a large amount by collecting the fund through religious activities and PADAYATHRA. This service shows the social responsibility of the mutt. Along with the social activities of the mutt it undertook several educational activities to the establishment of various educational institutions for the needy class in various parts of Karnataka state. Educational institutions of the mutt are as follows

1. Sri Jagadguru Renukacharya Gurukula Rambapuri.
2. Sri Jagadguru Renukacharya ITI Balehonnur.
3. Sri Jagadguru Rudramini Residential High School. Balehonnur.
4. Sri Jagadguru Shivananda hostel. Balehonnur.
5. Sri Jagadguru Renukacharya Rural High School. Shiggavi.
6. Sri Jagadguru Rambapuriswara High School Jalki, Bijapur.
7. Vedantha school, Sultanpuri, Gokak Taluk.
8. Sri Jagadguru Renukacharya Schools and Colleges at Bangalore.
9. Sri Jagadguru Shivanandashrama Trust, Birur.
10. Sri Jagadguru Abhinava Renuka mandira Davanagere.
11. Sri Mahanathi mutt Bangalore.
12. Sri Vibhuthi mutt Bangalore.
13. Sri Choudeswara Orphans students School Balehonnur.
14. Sri Vidhyabharathi Jnana mandira high school Chithradurga..
15. Jangama Jyothi Rambapuri.

About 55 schools and colleges are managed by the mutt. Nearly 3600 students are studying in these reputed organizations, Choudeswara Orphans students School Balehonnur is main charitable institution to give education to destitute children and bring them to main stream of the society. These institutions have 900 teachers and 450 supporting staff. Many of the institutions of the mutt have attracted the attention of the discerning public at the national level. In this organization there is no discrimination of caste creed sex and religion. Students are coming from all parts and corners of the nations.

Apart from spiritual, social and educational activities, the mutt has given importance to the growth and development of Kannada literature of the state, the mutt has published a number of books, journals and magazines under its publications namely, Gurukarunya, Sri Rambapuri Darshana, Sharabha charitha, Siddantha sikamani, Veeragama, Rambapuri Belagu, bi monthly magazine and etc. These are some main publications of Rambapuri mutt.

Thus, the mutt which has been centre of spiritual values also conducting social and educational activities across the state. And also it becomes the educational hub in the state. A number of educational institutions are managed by the mutt. The mutt has a number of orphanage centres, old age centres, residential schools, colleges' and professional colleges. The mutt is considering as Trividha DasohaI.e. providing education, food and shelter to the needy. The building constructed recently are named after various Jagadgurus like Shivananda, Jyothi, Shivajyothi, Veerajyothi, Pashupathi with an intention that devotees will stay during night at mutt.

In the month of October navarathri festival is being celebrated by the mutt. Ten days Dassara Darbar is being celebrated.in the name of Sharanavarathri. it is the most attractive rituals of the mutt. Ten days crowned Jagadguru of the mutt is taken for procession around Rambapuri and coronate at the peet in front of thousands of devotees and conducted some religious rituals. Three days festival and local fare are conducted. Dasara Darbar is one of the main event of the mutt. The social activities are carried out by the mutt like health camp, blood donation, eye checkup, health camp for cattle and pet animals and many more.

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